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DIFFERENTIATE YOUR TEACHING INSTRUCTION IN ESP CLASSROOM

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Abstract: Improvements in technology create new opportunities and challenges not only in societies but also in educational settings. Consequently, many pedagogical approaches have been introduced to meet students' needs. Regarding the need for new pedagogical approaches in L2 settings to enhance students' essential skills, the flipped learning approach has gained considerable attention from many language teachers, educators, and researchers. This article aims to provide a theoretical basis and demonstrate how the flipped learning approach can be used in English classrooms to improve students' engagement and other 21st-century skills. Additionally, it attempts to highlight the challenges encountered in its implementation.

Key words: Flipped learning, L2 education, 21st-century skills, student engagement, pedagogical approaches.

INTRODUCTION

Flipped learning, an alternative instructional strategy that integrates technology outside the classroom, has gained significant attention from academics and educators worldwide. English language instructors increasingly embrace this innovative approach as a viable option when designing their lesson plans.

This article highlights the four pillars of flipped learning, the essential components, and the defining characteristics of a flipped classroom. Additionally, it provides a brief history, theoretical background, and underlying principles of the approach. It also examines research on the implementation of flipped learning in diverse English language classroom settings where English is taught as a second or foreign language. Furthermore, the article explores how flipped learning enhances learners' engagement and fosters 21st-century skills. The following section delves into these aspects in detail.

Flipped learning has been applied in the field of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) to help students acquire a greater number of English idioms, promote active learning, increase motivation to communicate, improve speaking skills, and enhance satisfaction with the flipped approach (Hung, 2017). Research has also investigated the effects of flipped learning on other EFL-related areas, including English speaking (Li & Suwanthep, 2017), English writing (Ahmed, 2016), and reading comprehension (Abaeian & The Asian Journal of Applied Linguistics, 2017).

LITERATURE REVIEW

When Salma Khan used the phrase «Flip your class» in a 2010 TED Talk (Technology, Entertainment, Design Talk) or when Jon Bergmann and Aaron Sams published a book in 2012, flipped learning gained widespread recognition. However, the term «Flipped» or «Flipping» was originally used in Wesley Baker's 2000 academic study on learning management systems (LMS).

The phrase resurfaced in a scholarly study conducted by Tenneson and McGlasson in 2005. They described the flipped classroom as a blended learning environment that utilizes technology to provide students with more time for engaged discussion (Tenneson & McGlasson, 2005).

Later, in 2007, Jeremy Strayer completed his doctoral dissertation, focusing on contrasting the educational activities in a traditional classroom with those in a flipped classroom using an intelligent tutoring system. In 2012, he published his research on how instruction in an inverted classroom could affect collaboration, innovation, and task orientation. Since then, he has continued to study the use of flipped learning (Strayer, 2007, 2012).

Around the same time, in Woodland Park, Colorado, Jon Bergmann and Aaron Sams noticed that student absences were common due to the proximity of the school to their homes. As a solution, they explored strategies to reach every student, eventually introducing «vodcasting» videos for them (Bergmann & Sams, 2012). The outcome of this innovative approach suggested that students improved their exam performance. Eventually, the flipped classroom gained widespread recognition and was endorsed by numerous academics and educators worldwide.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The flipped learning approach stems from constructivist learning theory, which emphasizes students' roles in learning by helping them become active learners and increasing their participation in classes. This approach serves as the foundation of flipped learning. One of the key benefits of the flipped learning approach is that it transforms class time into interactive learning activities, where students ask questions about the material, collaborate with peers on practical exercises, and apply their knowledge to real-world scenarios.

Experienced educators in this field have identified the essential components of a flipped classroom that facilitate flipped learning. These include: professional educator, intentional content, flexible environment, learning culture (flipped learning network, 2014)

A flipped classroom fosters a dynamic learning environment characterized by multiple learning modes, such as group work, independent study, research, performance, and project-based work, all of which maximize students' learning potential. By engaging in diverse learning contexts, students can choose when and where to learn, gradually enhancing their autonomy and self-directed learning skills.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Since we entered the 21st century, there has been a shift from a teacher-centered to a student-centered approach in learning culture. In flipped classrooms, students have a fantastic opportunity to explore subjects deeply. Additionally, both inside and outside the classroom, students actively engage in acquiring new information and skills. They can take responsibility for their own education and learn at their own pace. Meanwhile, teachers can emphasize classroom interactions to ensure students understand each subject.

Intentional Content. In a flipped classroom, teachers play a significant role in determining what needs to be taught directly and what resources should be used to encourage independent exploration outside the classroom. To maximize class time, teachers carefully select specific content that allows students to experience various teaching strategies based on the subject matter and grade level. These strategies may include active learning, peer instruction, inquiry-based learning, project-based learning, or problem-based learning.

Professional Teachers. Experienced, competent, and professional teachers are more essential than ever, as selecting the right materials for a flipped classroom is critical. They must decide when and how to transition from traditional classroom instruction to student-directed learning. Additionally, they must determine how to facilitate communication between students, as well as between professors and students. Teachers in flipped classrooms frequently evaluate their teaching methods and collaborate with colleagues to enhance instruction and develop a shared understanding of key concepts taught in this format.

Learner's Responsibility. In a flipped learning model, students are encouraged to take ownership of their education. They are expected to support themselves and collaborate with their classmates, which can be challenging for those accustomed to passive learning through lectures. Furthermore, students in a flipped classroom are required to independently explore subject matter. Based on the learning opportunities provided by teachers, students must also develop their capacity for higher-order thinking.

Teacher's Position. In a flipped classroom, the traditional role of the teacher as the "sage on the stage" is generally replaced by the "guide on the side." As a result, teachers must be experts in their subject matter and skilled in engaging students. The flipped learning model shifts instruction outside of class time, giving teachers more opportunities to interact with learners and act as facilitators, coaches, mentors, or advisors within the classroom. Additionally, because students can learn at their own pace, teachers can provide more individualized feedback on academic progress and clarify misunderstandings.

Moreover, teachers play a crucial role in selecting authentic materials and producing content videos for students. They should also develop alternative assessment methods to help students demonstrate their knowledge in alignment with specific learning outcomes (Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

Material's Role. Videos and real-world materials are frequently used in flipped learning environments. These are the primary resources for transforming a traditional classroom, as they contain lessons and specific instructions. In this context, videos serve as excellent learning tools, enabling students to pursue independent study outside the classroom.

On the other hand, authentic materials can serve as valuable and meaningful learning resources for both in-class and out-of-class activities in a flipped classroom (Bergmann et al., 2012; Bergmann & Sams, 2012; Driscoll, 2012; Khan, 2012; Pacansky-Brock, 2013). These materials include news articles, advertisements, movies, songs, TV broadcasts, newspapers, and magazines.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Differentiating teaching instruction in an ESP (English for Specific Purposes) classroom is essential for addressing diverse learners' needs, professional goals, and varying language proficiency levels. Effective differentiation enhances student engagement, motivation, and overall language acquisition by integrating tailored content, adaptive teaching methods, and practical application strategies. By implementing learner-centered approaches, educators can create a dynamic and inclusive learning environment that fosters both linguistic and professional development.

To achieve this, it is crucial to conduct a thorough needs analysis to identify students' specific language requirements and professional objectives. Utilizing flexible teaching strategies, including task-based learning, collaborative projects, and technology-enhanced materials, helps accommodate different learning styles. Providing scaffolded learning support, such as guided practice and real-world simulations, allows students to bridge language gaps and gradually develop autonomy. The integration of authentic materials, such as industry-specific resources, case studies, and workplace communication tasks, enhances the relevance and applicability of ESP instruction. Additionally, ongoing assessment through formative evaluations and feedback mechanisms ensures continuous progress monitoring and enables instructors to adjust their strategies accordingly. By adopting these approaches, ESP instructors can create an effective, student-centered learning experience that meets the unique demands of specialized language learning.

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